

Tarascan Religion

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Purepecha, Tarascan, Tarascan, Language

It is an approach to the religion of the Tarascans-Uacusechas who inhabited western Mexico a few centuries before the arrival of Europeans. There are few historical sources available for this purpose, unlike other places in Mesoamerica. The most important source is the *Relación de Michoacán* of which unfortunately the first part dealing with the religion of this group was lost.

Date Range: 1300 CE - 1522 CE

Region: Irehecua (Tarascan Realm)

Region tags: Mexico, West Mexico

The map shows the largest extension of Irehecua, which the Spaniards translated as a kingdom, governed from the capital of Tzintzuntzan. It covered a little over 75,000 square kilometers, encompassing most of Michoacán and parts of neighboring states in present-day western Mexico.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Alcalá, J. (2008). *La Relación de Michoacán*. Colegio de Michoacán.
- Source 2: Corona Nuñez, J. (1946). *La religión de los tarascos*. *Anales Del Museo Michoacano*, 2a Época, IV, 13-38.
- Source 3: Espejel, C. (2008). *La Justicia y el Fuego*. *Dos claves para leer la Relación de Michoacán*. Colegio de Michoacán.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://etzakutarakua.colmich.edu.mx/proyectos/relaciondemichoacan/default.asp>
- Source 1 Description: This is a page that allows you to browse the most important data of the *Relación de Michoacán* including important facts about its religion.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SIWIIPV4AjY>
- Source 2 Description: Conference Punzo-Enkerlin : "Parhaquahpeni, la espalda del mundo, acercamiento a la visión ritual y social"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://bibliotecadigital.ilce.edu.mx/sites/fondo2000/vol1/relacion/html/indice.html>

– Source 1 Description: Third part of the Relación de Michoacán.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: I think so, since the texts always mention the prevalence of Curicuarei over the other gods both in the plane of gods and men.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The imposition of the Uacusecha was by means of violence in the first place in the zones of their influence.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: It was a government that was expanding and there were multiple conflicts on its various frontiers, especially to the east with the Mexica, in the area of the Toluca Valley and in the region of Cutzamala.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: It is not the case that the religious specializations were paid by the government, but that they formed a caste of which the calzonci himself was an integral part.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The concept of apostate is difficult to fit into this, since eventually all the Uacusecha nobles had to leave their religion and convert to Christianity.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Although the Franciscan friar Jerónimo de Alcalá collected the rituals and oral tradition of this group in Tzintzuntzan around 1540, the transmission of the knowledge of this group was oral through the priests who narrated these facts in their most important ceremonies.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

Notes: Refer to the entrance of Tzintzuntzan. This was a large capital where thousands of people lived and covers about 1000 hectares. Although there are multiple pyramids and plazas, the Great Platform stands out with its 5 yácatas (as these structures are called in Purépecha) of mixed plant in the upper part.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Yácatas

Notes: These were the main pyramids of this group. It is a rectangular structure with a circular attached that supported a tempo and a fire to praise their gods.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Perhaps the petroglyphs found throughout the city sometimes associated with terraces, roads, houses or pyramids are an important part of the religious iconography of this group.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Especially eagles were associated with their major gods, but also the representation of canids, possibly coyotes were very relevant.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: The representation of a man with a coyote mask is one of the most important

sculptural examples of the Tarascans. The presence of chacmol sculptures is also important in the region.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: In the petroglyphs, abstract motifs such as spirals, circles, or small wells are found by the hundreds in rocks throughout the ancient city, as well as in the yacatas themselves.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The Uacúsecha priests carried elements that were surely very important for their religion. In the first place, metal tweezers hung around their necks, a decorated cane and a gourd on their backs encrusted with turquoise, which they say represented all the people on their backs.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: The only representations of their principal gods Curicaueri and Xaratanga that are known without doubt through the plates of the Relación de Michoacan, the former is represented as a man and the latter as an older woman.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The yacatas of mixed plan are generally oriented to the west in their circular part and on the other hand, the axis of the quadrangular structures is oriented towards one of the highest and most important mountains of the Patzcuaro Lake basin.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Notes: The historical source is very much embedded in the Spanish vision, so we could think that it does exist, however I think it is very difficult to establish it conclusively,

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: The main lords among them the cazonci was cremated in the central patio in front of the 5 yacatas in Tzintzuntzan, together with a great amount of offerings.

Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: There is a reference to the preservation of a body of one of the main lords of Patzcuaro which was still venerated at the arrival of the Spaniards. This personage called Huquingare II is said to have been killed by lightning and "embalmed" and they had him as a god in the lake.

Interment:

– Field doesn't know

Cannibalism:

– Yes

Notes: There are several passages in the historical sources where cannibalism is mentioned,

although this is a highly debated topic. In the archaeological record of Tzintzuntzan what we have is the presence of multiple mechanical treatments for fleshing and thermal treatments such as the boiling of bones, but this is not data that allows us to ensure this.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: In the *Relacion de Michoacan* it is mentioned that many of those sacrificed in the feast of Cuingo were taken to the "herbazales" where they were left out in the open to be eaten by birds such as vultures and coyotes and these were dedicated to the "Dios del Infierno" (God of Hell).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: In the *Relacion de Michoacan* it is mentioned that many of those sacrificed in the feast of Cuingo were taken to the "herbazales" where they were left out in the open to be eaten by birds such as vultures and coyotes and these were dedicated to the "Dios del Infierno" (God of Hell).

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: There are several examples of this, but the most important is undoubtedly the presence of the Tzintzuntzan ossuary, which is a layer of crushed human bone more than 30 meters long by 1.5 meters deep and 3 meters wide. This type of deposit, unique for its magnitude in Mesoamerica, is part of the construction system of the Great Platform of Tzintzuntzan.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: There are many examples of this. We know in the sources that there was for example a "Tzompantli", where human skulls were exposed in the Great Platform of Tzintzuntzan, at the same time it is mentioned the existence of special houses to keep bones. For example in the feast of Unihizperánsquaro the bones of the captives were veiled in the so called "houses of the popes" that we suppose were the rooms and places for the cult that the priests had in Tzintzuntzan.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: It is frequently mentioned how in different festivities human sacrifices were made of people who on the one hand made transgressions and on the other hand, those captured for this purpose in attacks on conquered peoples.

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: It is frequently mentioned how in different festivities human sacrifices were made of people who on the one hand made transgressions on the other hand when an important lord and especially the cazonci died a large number of his servants were buried with him to serve him in the afterlife.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: It is mentioned in the historical source that the cazonci had pumas, jaguars, coyotes, wolves, and eagles, and when these were large they killed them and brought others. Unfortunately, none of these animals have been found buried.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: A large number of burials have been found in the area of the 5 yácatas of Tzintuntzan. In the offerings, objects possibly used by the personage have been found, such as arrows, axes, spindle whorls, etc.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: A large number of burials have been found in the area of the 5 yácatas of Tzintuntzan. Sumptuary objects have been found in the offerings, such as ear flares and besotes made of obsidian, gold, and turquoise, as well as many necklaces, headdresses, etc. It is worth mentioning that the use of metals was very widespread in this group and had a very high value among the people of this group.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Although rare, a burial of an adult individual was recently found under a house in one of the peripheral neighborhoods of the city of Tzintzuntzan. However, this is rare.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Between the main yacatas

Notes: Los señores más importantes eran cremados y luego depositados al pie de las yacatas rodeados de un ricas ofrendas y muchas personas sacrificadas, decían para este no tocara la tierra.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The only representation we have of Curicaueri, his main deity, is anthropomorphic in a drawing of the Relación de Michoacán. However, in the text it always mentions to me that he is represented by an obsidian knife.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There are examples of gods appearing to man in various forms, whether human or animal.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - No

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms and behavior were very important among the Uacusechas. This consisted of prayer and bringing firewood to the temple for the gods, as well as not getting drunk.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Getting drunk and constantly having sex with multiple partners was judged as morally wrong behavior in the eyes of the priests and uacusecha lords.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Getting drunk and constantly having sex with multiple partners was judged as morally wrong behavior in the eyes of the priests and uacusecha lords.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: The Uacusecha used to sacrifice the ears and with this blood they fed their gods.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: The Uacusecha used to sacrifice their ears and with this blood, they fed their gods.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

↳ Commoners:

– Yes

↳ Elites:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Prayer and the time dedicated to this and to bringing firewood to the temple were highly valued as important ethical virtues.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Prayer and the time dedicated to this and to bringing firewood to the temple were highly valued as important ethical virtues.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Prayer in the special houses for this purpose was very important and seems to be a very private practice that seems according to the historical source had to do with long periods of vigil.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The duration of some festivities such as the Equata Conscuaro took at least days or that of Sicudiro which took 5 days.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, it is important to mention that the cazonci was considered the representation of Curicaueri the main god on earth.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Although the term is much debated whether the Tarascans can be considered a state or an empire, it seems to me that it is best to keep the Purepecha term Irechequa (which could be translated as the domains of the lord).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know that the tributes were kept in the granaries of the Cazonci, however we do not know if

these food surpluses could have been distributed through some mechanism.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Among the Tarascans-Uacúsechas there was a very well-defined religious structure. This was headed by the Petamuti -the high priest- and under him there were other specialized positions such as the curizitacha who placed the incense in the ceremonies, the thiuimencha who carried the gods, the áxamencha who were the sacrificers among others.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Among the Tarasco-Uacúsechas there was a very well-defined structure in the organization of the government. This was directed by the Cazonci who represented their main god Curicaueri. Under this there were different orders of government, there was a general captain of war, 4 main lords in the borders, and a very important position were the caciques of the provinces and the Ocambecha who

were in charge of collecting the tribute. In addition to these, each craft had its own organization.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: The historical source points more to the fact that the storage of food was in charge of the structure of the Cazonci, we cannot rule out the role of the religious in these tasks.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The historical source points more to the fact that the storage of food was in charge of the structure of the Cazonci, we cannot rule out the role of the religious in these tasks.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There was a special person in charge of collecting taxes called Ocambecha, who depended on the Cazonci.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Apparently, the people who led those who were going to be sacrificed were not part of the religious structure, however, along with them went the so-called hatapatiecha, who went singing and proclaiming in front of them.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: At least part of the justice was imparted by the high priest the Petámuti, since it is mentioned that through the use of mirrors or the reflection in the water, the priests could see the transgressions of certain people and the priest was the one who carried out the acts of justice accordingly. Most of the sentences were dictated by the Cazonci.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As already mentioned this was shared between the religious structure and that of the Cazonci. In general, it could be said that ultimately the Cazonci was the one who had the authority to exercise justice and dictate punishments accordingly, although this was executed most of the time by priests. Except on rare occasions it is mentioned that the high priest had the power to exercise justice directly.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: There are many references to punishments for different transgressions, ranging from removing insignia to cutting or mutilating parts of the body, to death.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifice was not only exclusive to captives in war, but the most important transgressions were punished by the cazonci with death.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: It is mentioned that lords who had committed a serious transgression, but did not deserve death, had their insignia of power removed and were exiled together with their wives.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: It is mentioned that there were transgressions that were punishable by imprisonment and physical punishment such as tearing the ears, and mutilating this could be done three times if it was repeated a fourth time the punishment was death.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: To the principal lords who were condemned to death by the cazonci, their entire "estate" was taken by the latter. Likewise, the insignia of power such as besotes and earmuffs were the property of the cazonci.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to establish. The historical source mentions that the different towns and lords sent their people to war, but it does not mention what kind of process may have existed for that purpose. These armies were always accompanied by religious men specialized in carrying the gods to battles.

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The historical source mentions that the different towns and lords sent their people to war, but it does not mention what kind of process may have existed for that purpose. These armies were always accompanied by religious men who specialized in carrying the gods to battles.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As the local caciques paid tribute to the cazonci in Tzintzuntzan, we believe that they were somehow under his military protection. Perhaps the best example of this is when Matlatzingas lords come to ask the cazonci Tzitzipandacuare for his protection against the Mexica by giving him this land on the border for his settlement.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: There are mentions in historical sources where it seems that time was measured in a period of 20-day moons. If this was so, the Tarasco-Uacusechas were supposed to have had a calendar organized in 18 twenties plus 5 complementary days to have a cycle of 365 days as in other parts of Mesamerica.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are mentions in historical sources where it seems that time was measured in a period of 20-day moons. If this was so, the Tarasco-Uacusechas were supposed to have had a calendar organized in 18 twenties plus 5 complementary days to have a cycle of 365 days as in other parts of Mesamerica.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tarascan Religion, Alcalá, Jerónimo. *La Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

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